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"EKONOMSKI IZAZOVI ZEMALJA U TRANZICIJI"

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STUDY OF THE TAX WEDGE IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA, SERBIA AND MONTENEGRO USING CLUSTER ANALYSIS

SUMMARY

Taxation through income tax is an extremely sensitive segment of the country's tax system. The most common method of determining the actual tax burden is the tax wedge. The tax wedge is a significant part of labour costs and represents the difference between gross wage and the net take – home pay. Despite quite strong economic performance in recent years, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro have not experienced significant improvements in their labor markets. The aim of this paper is to investigate the amount of the tax wedge in three out of the six Western Balkan countries and analyze the possibilities for redcing tax burden. The cluster analysis was conducted on a sample of 28 countries, resulting in three groups of countries classified according to their tax wedge and unemployment rate. Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro belong to the second group of clusters, which is right after the group of countries with the highest tax wedge and rate of unemployment. The paper contains recommendations for the reform of fiscal policy and the conclusions relevant to the conducted research.

Key words: *tax wedge, labour costs, unemployment rate, transition countries, hierarchical cluster analysis.*

JEL: *H24, J32, J38*

1. INTRODUCTION

Persistent unemployment has been a major blot on the economic and social record of most countries, during the past two decades or more. By extending the global economic crisis (2008), taxation of labor, together with the phenomenon of unemployment, becomes an open question in all transition countries. The need to reduce the economic and financial crisis has sparked an expansive fiscal policy. Some of the transition countries have opted for tax cuts while some countries, much burdened by the crisis have pretended to increase taxes. In a large number of cases, fiscal policy implied an increase in tax incentives, not a reduction in tax rates. The repercussions of so conceived fiscal systems were high tax burden or tax wedge.

There are several definitions for the tax wedge phenomenon. In most papers, the tax wedge is calculated as the sum of income tax for individuals and all social contributions as a percentage of total labor costs and does not include consumption tax rates. The OECDs Taxing wages publications defines the tax wedge as the sum of personal income tax plus employers social security contributions together with any payroll tax less cash transfers, expressed as a percentage of labour cost. The tax wedge can be calculated as the difference between gross labour costs and net take home pay in relation to the gross labour costs. Simplified, the tax wedge is the difference between the gross labor costs borne by the employer and the net salary of employees. The tax wedge represents the total tax burden on labor. The tax burden on the workforce is an important instrument of the tax policy, because of consequently influence on employment. By increasing the tax wedge, there is an increase in the cost of labor employed by the employer. Such circumstances di-

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rectly determine the employer's decision for employment. So there is an increase in unemployment. This generally accepted assumption of positive correlation between tax wedge and unemployment has been empirically investigated by numerous scientists. On the basis of the results by eminent researchers, this study analyzes the causal consequence link between two phenomena mentioned above. The paper starts from the assumption that the tax wedge is inherently important factor which negatively affects employment. The subject of this paper is the analysis of the tax wedge and the unemployment rate in transition countries: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro. The main goal of this paper is to investigate in which countries the highest tax burden figures.

The paper gives an overview of current theoretical literature and current empirical research of the tax wedge. It is emphasized the effects of tax burden on the labor market. Cluster analysis was conducted using data from statistical data bases of International Monetary Fund, data from the OECD and EU data base. Data of the unemployment rate and tax wedge for transition countries have been incorporated on the basis of the current data base of the Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Bosnia and Herzegovina and Statistical Office of Montenegro. The research will divide the countries into certain groups with common characteristics. Finally, the paper contains recommendations for the reform of fiscal policy and the conclusions relevant to the conducted research.

2. Related literature

Although, the tax wedge has begun to attract academic attention over the past few years, there are a number of theoretical, empirical and experimental research that examines personal income taxation. "The income taxation is the most significant source of tax revenue in developing and developed economies" (Đurović Todorović, Đorđević, 2008, p. 73). The tax wedge extensively becomes part of the research circles as a very important element that affects the country's competitiveness in its "competition" on the international labor market.

The analysis starts with an influential work that investigates a negative influence of the tax wedge, presented by Vork et al. Vork et al. (2006) find influences of the tax wedge on employment rates, activity rates, working hours, unemployment rates and the share of parttime workers. A survey conducted by Behar (2009) encompassed the analysis of new members of the European Union. The paper examines the differences in the outcomes of the labor market, tax wedges and the advantages of the member states of the European Union. The relationship between taxes, benefits and employment was examined using data from statistically transparent databases of new members of the European Union (10). Within the new members, authors of non-parametric analysis find that tax wedges and the duration of benefits (not the replacement ratio) are associated with poor labor market outcomes. Tvrdon (2011) found out a negative correlation between tax wedge and employment rate in OECD countries. Most studies find a negative relationship between marginal effective tax indicators and employment rates, particularly for the youth –where separately explored (Behar, 2009; Dolenc and Laporšek, 2010). The paper of Gabrilo (2016) studying the tax wedge in Croatia, Belgium, Estonia, Germany and Slovakia. The work gives the decomposition of a net average tax wedge using the OECD's methodology, and the results indicate the progressiveness of taxation. The progressivity of taxation is absent only in Germany, and as a consequence, the high base of social security contributions is stated. The results of the survey show that the lowest tax burden (single person, no children) in Croatia, followed by Estonia, Slovakia, Germany and Belgium. Tax wedge in Croatia, Austria, Hungary, Poland and Greece was studied by Onorato (2016). The work provides a comparative overtake of tax burden in analyzed countries in 2013. Using the OECD's Taxing Wages methodology, the author made a calculation of the net average tax wedge, net average tax rates and other indicators for hypothetical units with different gross wages. The results of the survey show that Croatia has the lowest tax wedge on wages below the average gross salary, and for salaries above the average lowest wedge in Poland. Šimović and Škrbić (2015) provide an analysis of changes in tax rates of income tax and contributions in Croatia. The authors give an analysis

of the impact of the tax rate projection on the total tax burden in Croatia. The results of their research show that the bulk of the overall tax burden relates to social contributions. In addition, according to authors, the most balanced distribution of tax burden can be achieved with a lower number of tax rates or with lower tax rates.

According to Tripeski and Tashevskaja (2012), OECD and EU countries can be classified into two groups, one with high tax wedge, high unemployment rate and low employment rate, and the other one with opposite characteristics. This study emphasized that the high tax wedge has detrimental effects on labour market outcomes. A cluster analysis performed on 43 countries (member of OECD, EU and EU candidates) shown us that higher tax wedge usually corresponds to higher levels of unemployment and lower levels of employment. Dolenc and Vodopivec (2005) deal with the following issues: the tax wedges, unemployment rates and employment in the OECD countries in the past; a tax wedge policy in old and new EU members; tax laws in Slovenia and their impact on unemployment. The results of their research have ranked the OECD countries in two parts. The first is made up of countries with a high tax wedge and high unemployment rates, and the second involves whole countries with low tax wedges and low unemployment rates. The authors came to the conclusion that EU Member States have more tax-exempt work compared to OECD countries, and, moreover, higher unemployment rates. How the tax wedge affects the unemployment rate in Croatia, Šeparovic (2009) gave in his research. The author emphasized that a tax wedge should be reduced if country wants to solve the problem of unemployment.

3. Methodology and data

If the tax wedge is large and net wages are too low, workers may be discouraged from participating in the regulated part of the labor market, finding outside options – unemployment or unregistered, informal work which is more attractive. The tax wedge on labor provides a measure of the extent to which the social protection and tax systems can discourage employment.

How we can express tax wedge? According to Festa (2015), the real labour cost (RLC) can be expressed as the following equality:

$$RLC = \frac{W(1+\tau f)}{P} \quad (1)$$

The real consumption wage (RCW), received by the worker, has the following expression:

$$RCW = \frac{W(1-\tau w) \cdot (1-t_i)}{P \cdot (1+t_c)} \quad (2)$$

Where W is nominal gross wage; P stands for GDP deflator, τf is the social security contribution rate paid by the employer, τw is the social contribution rate paid by the worker, t_i is the tax rate on labour income and t_c is the consumption rate on goods and services .

When we summarize the equation (1) and (2) we have the measure of tax wedge:

$$TW = \frac{(1+\tau f) \cdot (1+t_c)}{(1-\tau w) \cdot (1-t_i)} \quad (3)$$

Equivalently,

$$RLC = \lambda \cdot RCW \quad (4)$$

Where,

$$\lambda = \frac{(1+\tau f) \cdot (1+t_c)}{(1-\tau) \cdot (1-t_i)} \quad (\text{Festa, 2015}). \quad (5)$$

Accordingly, an increase in the personal income tax and social security contributions is expressed by the tax wedge. An increase in consumption tax is a capricious issue, since some authors consider that the tax on consumption should be seen as a determinant of the tax wedge, while another group of authors does not agree with it.

The tax wedge can also be calculated as the difference between gross labour costs and net take – home pay in relation to the gross labour costs (Dolenc & Vodopivec, 2005; Šeparović, 2009; Trpeski & Tashevskaja, 2012).

$$TW = \frac{GLC - NP}{GLC} \quad (6)$$

Where TW is the tax wedge, GLC is the gross labour costs and NP is net take-home pay. In accordance with this tax wedge calculation methodology, the complete picture of the tax wedge in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro is shown in the table below (Table 1). The table also provides a parallel overview of the unemployment rate in the analyzed countries in the period 2015-2017.

Table 1: Total tax wedge on labour and unemployment rate in transition countries: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro (in %), 2015-2017.

Country	Tax wedge			Unemployment rate		
	2015	2016	2017	2015	2016	2017
Bosnia and Herzegovina	34.59	34.60	34.74	27.70	25.40	20.50
Serbia	27.33	27.37	27.4	17.7	15.3	13.5
Montenegro	33.79	33.55	33.33	17.6	17.7	16.1

**Note: Tax wedge for single person at 100% of average earnings, no child is taken into account.*

Source: International Monetary Fund, World Economic Outlook Database, April 2018; database of Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia; Bulletin Public Finances of the Republic of Serbia, April 2018; Federal Bureau of Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Author's calculations.

Table 1 presents the tax wedge and unemployment rates in the period 2015-2017. The table provides an insight to the differences in the tax wedge and unemployment rates among countries. Bosnia and Herzegovina has the highest tax wedge (34.74%) and the highest unemployment rate (20.50) in 2017. In Montenegro the tax wedge in 2017 was reduced at around 33%, which was similar as in Bosnia and Herzegovina. For a single worker who earns an average income, the labour tax wedge in Serbia in 2017 was 27.33. In Serbia the tax wedge in 2017 was lower than in Montenegro and Bosnia and Herzegovina.

In 2007, three out of the six Western Balkan countries covered by this study radically changed their systems of labour taxation. Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro face with similar economic and labor market challenges. Specifically, countries have some of the highest unemployment rates in Europe.

Graph 1: Tax wedge on labour in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro, 2015-2017.

Source: *International Monetary Fund, World Economic Outlook Database, April 2018; database of Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia; Bulletin Public Finances of the Republic of Serbia, April 2018; Federal Bureau of Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Author's calculations.*

In this paper we used the data from the OECD and Statistical Office data base of analyzed transition countries. First we made a descriptive analysis of the size of labor tax wedge and its components in Bosnia and

Herzegovina. Then, we made an international comparison of the tax wedge for 25 EU countries, members of OECD, and Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro. Then we analyzed the tax wedge and its relations with the unemployment rate using cluster analysis. We have used the hierarchical cluster analysis in order to find some similarities among countries in terms of tax wedge and unemployment rate.

4. Results and discussions: Country Clustering

First we aim to analyze the tax wedge evolution in Bosnia and Herzegovina in the past three years, as well as its components. Table 2 presents the level of the tax wedge in Bosnia and Herzegovina between 2015-2017. Based on Law on contributions of the Federation BIH social security contribution rates are given below.

Table 2: Social security contributions in Bosnia and Herzegovina (in %), 2018.

Type of Insurance	Rate (%)
Contribution for pension and invalid insurance	18.5%
Contribution for health insurance	12%
Contribution for unemployment insurance	1.0%
Contribution for child protection	1.5%

Source: *Official Gazette of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina 34/18, Law on contributions.*

The Personal income tax rate in Bosnia and Herzegovina is 10%. As we can see, tax wedge in this country was situated around the value 34% between 2015-2016, and in 2017 it shows a slight increase, getting to 34,74.

Graph 2: Total tax wedge on labour in Europe, 2017 (in %)

Source: *International Monetary Fund, World Economic Outlook Database, April 2018; database of Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia; Bulletin Public Finances of the Republic of Serbia, April 2018; Federal Bureau of Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina; OECD (2018). Author's calculations.*

Graph 2 gives a picture of the tax burden on work in 25 Europe countries, OECD members, and in transition countries: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro. For a single worker, who earns average income, the tax wedge in Serbia in 2017 was 27.4%, in Bosnia and Herzegovina 33.33% and in Montenegro 34.74%. The largest tax wedge among countries in 2017 was in Belgium (53.7%), while the smallest tax wedge was recorded in Switzerland (21%). The highest unemployment rate was recorded in Greece by 2017 (21.5), while the lowest rate was recorded by Ireland (2.8).

Based on the analysis of statistical data, it can be concluded that countries with high unemployment rates coherently have a higher tax wedge compared to countries with low unemployment rates. However, that descriptive statistics would not give wrong conclusions, cluster analysis was conducted through appropriate statistical tools and groups of analyzed countries with similar characteristics were defined. Two variables are taken into account: unemployment rate and tax wedge. The analyzed variables are tax wedge at 100% average wage level and unemployment rate in the period 2015-2017. The cluster analysis was run on a sample of 28 countries. In order to calculate the distance of the data the squared Euclid distance measure was used. We used Within Groups Linkage's method to calculate the similarity of the data. The analysis produced three clusters, presented graphically by a dendrogram (Figure 1). The characteristics and basic descriptive statistics of the three clusters are presented in table 3. The second cluster shows best labour market performance. Namely, the lowest unemployment rate and the lowest tax wedge. The average unemployment rate in 2017 is 5.044% and the average tax wedge is 33.6889%. It consists of 9 countries.

Figure 1: Dendrogram using hierarchical clustering of countries

Source: Author's calculations using SPSS.

Table 3: Characteristics of the three groups of countries obtained by hierarchical clustering

Group	Tax wedge			Unemployment rate		
	2015	2016	2017	2015	2016	2017
Cluster 1 (n = 14)	45.38±4.5	45.10±4.1	44.92±3.9	8.80±2.56	8.15±2.58	7.33±2.55
Cluster 2 (n = 9)	34.08±5.72	33.96±5.78	33.68±5.59	6.27±1.78	5.84±1.50	4.04±1.11
Cluster 3 (n = 5)	34.84±4.91	35.07±5.23	35.11±5.30	22.02±4.45	20.34±4.15	17.76±3.26
Total (n = 28)	39.86±7.41	39.73±7.23	39.56±7.14	10.35±6.24	9.58±5.79	8.46±5.06

Source: Author's calculations using SPSS.

The hierarchical clustering method is Within Groups Linkage and the distance function is the square Euclid distance. The characteristics of the first cluster are high tax wedge and high unemployment rates, compared to the Cluster 2 and Cluster 3. The highest unemployment rate in this group is registered in Greece – 21.5%. Belgium stands out as one of the countries with the highest tax wedge -53.95%. The starting assumption is an empirical proved. Analyzed countries with a high tax wedge have a high unemployment rate. The second cluster is formed mainly from the developing countries, including Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro. The structure tax forms in transition countries abounds with numerous weaknesses. Transition countries are classified in the second cluster (Table 3). The second group of clusters is right after the group of countries with the highest tax wedge and rate of unemployment. Subsumed under second cluster, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro must initiate a fiscal relaxation process.

5. CONCLUSION

The aim of this overview is to underscore the role of the tax wedge on labour market. As regards to the link between tax wedge and unemployment rate, the existing research generally fails to find evidence even though there are few studies that investigate this link. Namely, there are no widely accepted results and further research is needed. The paper analyzes the 25 European countries and three transition countries. The paper is based on a descriptive analysis of the unemployment rate and the quantitative tax wedge calculation in analyzed countries for the period 2015 to 2017. We conducted a cluster analysis that divided the analyzed countries into three groups based on common characteristics. The variables we observed were the tax wedge and the unemployment rate. The results are as follows. The second and third clusters show similar characteristics and a more favorable economic environment than the second cluster. The first cluster is a set of fourteen countries with the highest tax wedges and the highest unemployment rates. Belgium is the country with the highest tax wedge. Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and Montenegro belong to the second group of clusters, which is right after the group of countries with the highest tax wedge and rate of unemployment. The theoretical analysis was supported by an empirical analysis which confirmed the starting assumption in the paper, positive correlation between the tax wedge and the unemployment rate. Large labor costs were reportedly followed by high unemployment rates. The unemployment rates in analyzed transition countries are much higher than the average of OECD member countries. Namely, according to the unemployment rate, Bosnia and Herzegovina is right behind Greece. So, it is listed among the countries that have the highest unemployment rates. Tax system reforms are necessary in all analyzed countries.

There are several ways to improve the fiscal position. If we start from the fact that every developing country relies heavily on indirect taxes, one of the way to reduce tax burden is a fiscal devaluation. This term must be based on a previously neutral change in the tax structure that relates to the reduction of the labor tax and the increase of the consumption tax. In transition countries, the highest share in consumption taxes has the Value added tax. By increasing the tax rate of the Value added tax, the state could reduce the tax burden.

In the OECD study, it was estimated that a previously neutral structure change, from the tax on income to consumption taxes, would impact on the increase in the long-term growth rate by 0.25-1%. Burgert & Roeger (2014) explored these effects. If the state exerts a previously neutral reduction of social security contributions and an increase in the Value added tax, there will be positive reflections on economic growth and employment. The reform would show negative results in a short period of time, but in the long run the result would be positive. There would be positive effects on increasing employment and reducing the unemployment rate. In the long-term period, a reduction in social security contributions would lead to a reduction in the costs of employers or the tax wedge. Therefore, there will be an increase in competitiveness on labor market and better positions of transition countries in the international framework.

The improvement of fiscal policy, apart from the level of public revenues, implies the efficient management of public expenditures. Therefore, it is necessary that states also influence the reduction of public expenditures through a comprehensive analysis of their structure and justification. In addition, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of the tax administration in order to reduce the tax wedge.

SAŽETAK

Oporezivanje kroz porez na dohodak je izuzetno osjetljiv segment poreskog sistema u zemlji. Najčešći način utvrđivanja stvarnog poreznog opterećenja je porezni klin. Porezni klin je značajan dio troškova rada i predstavlja razliku između bruto zarade i neto plate. Uprkos prilično snažnom ekonomskom rastu posljednjih nekoliko godina, Bosna i Hercegovina, Srbija i Crna Gora nisu osjetile značajna poboljšanja na tržištu rada. Cilj ovog rada je da se ispita iznos poreznog klina u tri od šest država Zapadnog Balkana te da se analiziraju mogućnosti smanjenja poreznog opterećenja. Sprovedena je klaster analiza na uzorku od 28 država gdje su države svrstane u tri grupe prema njihovom poreznom klinu i stopi nezaposlenosti. Bosna i Hercegovina, Srbija i Crna Gora pripadaju drugoj grupi klastera, koja je odmah poslije grupe zemalja sa najvećim poreznim klinom i stope nezaposlenosti. Ovaj rad sadrži preporuke za reformu fiskalne politike i zaključke relevantne sprovedenom istraživanju.

Ključne riječi: *poreski klin, troškovi rada, stopa nezaposlenosti, tranzicijske zemlje, hijerarhijska klaster analiza.*

JEL: *H24, J32, J38*

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